

THE INTERPRETATION OF THE ORPHAN PROTAGONISTS IN THE WORKS OF KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOEV IN MODERN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Annotation: In this article, in the works of Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev, a bright figure of children's literature, the biographic information taken from his life and the social problems of that time are studied through the depiction of the theme of "orphanhood" and the interpretation of the image of "orphan boy". The ideas expressed by the author through the image of the "orphan" are also analyzed

Key words: children's life, orphan, orphanhood, internal monologue, biographical information, protagonist, novel.

One of the most well-known authors of Uzbek children's literature, Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev, is regarded as a writer who perfectly captured the character and mentality of children in his works. He was a beloved children's author who brought Uzbek children's literature to the world level. The characters created by the writer live in the hearts of many readers with their unique personality traits. In particular, his heroes such as Hashimjon, Orifjon, Akrom, Zafar who have already become well-known to young readers, have been translated into different languages and won the love not only of Uzbek children, but also of children of various nationalities. The reason is that the traits of these characters is remarkably bright, cheerful, innocent and simple-minded, especially the inclination to humor, laughter, jokes, made the nature of the character even brighter.¹

Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev loved the world of children, he tried to be very close to them, by his own admission, he tried to "steal words from the language of his little friends." His works has been attracting the attention of literary critics for a long time. Every new work of his that saw the face of the press never went unnoticed. Scientific articles by O. Sharafiddinov, A. Rasulov, M. Koshjanov, U. Normatov, S. Mamajonov, P. Shermuhamedov, as well as the works of many researchers of children's literature, can be cited as an example.²

Khudoyberdi was orphaned at an early age and raised by his grandparents. In his "Biographical Records" it is written:

¹ (Jumaboyev, 2006)

² (To'laboyeva, 2019)

"I was born on December 17, 1932 in the village of Katta Tagob in Fergana region. My father Tokhtavoy died at the age of 21 in Chorku, Tajikistan. Two years later, my mother Sorabibi's aunt Ashirbibi died and her five children were orphaned, so she married Usta Kadir (this was the decision of the relatives). I was brought up by my grandfather Erkavoy and my mother Robiyabibi. Some of my spirit, behavior and character were formed thanks to my grandfather, a gardener, and my mother, a storyteller."³

Therefore, in some of his works, he mentioned the topic of orphanhood and narrated about the fate of orphans. Among these were his novels "Little Chairman", "The Boy with Five Children", "Paradise People" and "Sad Eyes". In these works, it is also possible to see that the author was based on biographical information from his own life. From the point of view of illuminating the psyche of the characters, in the works of the writer, child psychology was realized mainly through the flow of thoughts and feelings and internal monologue, the emphasis was placed on the inner experiences of orphans. Khudoyberdi also told about the years of his orphaned childhood, which left bitter memories in his life. For example, the work "A boy with five children" is based on biographical information, it describes the life of people and complex social and economic situations during the Second World War. The protagonist of "The Boy with Five Children" goes through life's difficult trials. When he and his five siblings lost their parents, they burned in the fire of orphanhood. In particular, six orphaned children, whose mothers died, hugging each other and feel the first shock of life. They clearly understand the need to be close to each other, to listen and understand each other. Later, fate brings them to more difficult trials. In the orphanage, they are divided. Even so, these children continue to help each other in their desire to reunite. Khudoyberdi described his childhood in the image of a hero who suffered from the harsh trials of life. "During the Second World War, 12-year-old Khudoyberdi was among those who were sent to Tashkent from the Kokan orphanage and wandered in the capital's orphanages. After being thrown off the train, Kh. Tukhtaboev was among those who crossed the road to Kokan on foot and endured the pain of the road and hunger."⁴ The writer writes down these events in his life in the form of Orifboy's difficulties. In this novel, in the image of the "orphan boy", human qualities such as courage, hard work, hope for the future, kindness, honesty are glorified.

³ (Mirvaliyev S., Shokirova R., 2016)

⁴ (Rasulov, 2009)

In the writer's work "Paradise People", the characters of pious and learned people like Grandfather Erka and Grandfather Matmusa are lovingly depicted. The reason for this is that his grandparents made a great contribution to the development of the writer's spirituality. This work is also a biographical work related to the author's life. The author tries to explain in the novel, how difficult orphanhood is for children, and that even though there are people around the orphan child who love and care for him, the child needs his own parents, without them, the child feels himself half-hearted. This can be deeply felt in this following extract:

"- Ah, mom?! - I said, I stood still for a breath. Oh, it's true, it's true! he is standing by the wall with his palm on his forehead. I recognized her from the velvet dress on her, and the woolen scarf on her head is hers! I screamed, "My mom, my mummy." We both started running towards each other. I fell twice before going down the hill. I don't have much time, so much...

Here we are, almost.

"Mum!" I shouted.

"My dear, my honey," my mother cried. We got tired. We are kissing, we are crying, he is carrying me, I am hugging his neck tightly...

- Did you miss me?

- I missed you, I missed you so much, honey.

- I missed you too, I missed you with these eyes. I miss you at night, I miss you when I'm playing, I want to see you every day. Then I cry and cry silently without showing my granny. Won't you leave me anymore?⁵

In the novel "Sad eyes" Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboev reveals the secret of a ruined house. The Zafar family is suddenly in decline: the father is caught with a bribe, the crimes of the mother, a gold merchant engaged in illegal trade, begin to be exposed. Unexpected events that took place made the boys confused: Akbar was locked in his room and remained silent, Zafar with his aunt and his dog went to one court and another office, Zafar remained alone with himself, Nigora was ignored. The tragedy deepened: the mother died in prison. Children fell as if from heaven to earth: became orphans. The events that caused the father to go to prison for a long time, and the mother to go to the immortal world, confused the children. Especially this blow affected Akbar worst of all. He just wanted a change of scenery. Yes, the environment has changed completely. They lost their father, mother, family friends, wealth, comfort, whatever their rich parents gave them. Now they were completely alone and deserted. A

⁵ (To'xtaboyev, 2015)

teenage spirit cannot handle this conflict. A fracture occurs in his psyche, as a result of which the boy burns himself. Psychological tragedy in a child occurs in this form. ⁶Although this work is not mainly focused on revealing the image of an "orphan", it describes how orphanhood puts children in a difficult situation, and how the child's psyche can bear tragic losses.

Analyzing the theme of "orphanage" and the image of an "orphan" in Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboev's works, we can see that his life journey and experiences were the factors that inspired him to write, played an important role in the formation of his writing talent and skills and gave his works a unique color and shine. The image in the center of the analysis serves as a symbol in the writer's works that teaches children positive qualities and reveals the socio-political problems of its time.

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